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RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Autonomous Timing and Orbit Determination for Microsatellite Constellations (ATOMIC)</i>
Project TA identifier	TA10-339
General application	Space
Type of test	SEE, Protons
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Date(s) of the experiment	04.-06.10.2024
Facility	PSI (PIF)
Amount of access granted	8h

Objectives of the experiments

The ATOMIC satellite payload, a fully autonomous on-board orbit determination and time synchronization (ODTS) system, is designated to be launched in a low Earth orbit (LEO) on the AIOTY microsatellite developed by Rapid Cubes GmbH, Berlin. It consists of a GNSS receiver, a chip-scale atomic clock (CSAC), an ARM Cortex-M7 microcontroller and an interface board providing power conditioning, latch-up protection and line driver. Note that as the CSAC is the only component which is already purchased as a radiation-tolerant version with space missions as potential use case stated by the manufacturer, this hardware component is not mounted on the payload board for the experiment and thus also not evaluated here.

The motivation of the experiment is to validate the hardware functionality in LEO, an environment with a high radiation. As only commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) components are used for ATOMIC, a characterization of single-event effects (SEEs) is foreseen, to test general suitability and reliability for the payload mission under the influence of radiation. Furthermore, the functionality of the latch-up protections is to be tested, i.e. the switch-off a reset of the individual hardware components in case of a high current consumption. In general, the proton irradiation tests aim to specifically look for Single Event Latch-ups (SEL) and Single Events Upsets (SEU). A Total Ionizing Dose (TID) evaluation is not part of this campaign and will be performed independently.

Experiment test report

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1. Introduction

The evaluation was carried out in four different experiments, each with its own hardware setup. The following sub-sections describe each experiment, including the test setup, results as tables and figures as well as a short discussion of the results. For all experiments, telemetry messages from the microcontroller unit (MCU) and – if applicable – from the GNSS receiver are recorded. The MCU transmits e.g. individual current consumption values for the MCU itself, the GNSS receiver and the antenna. Furthermore, the overall power consumption of the payload is recorded using a multimeter.

2. ATOMIC Board with GNSS receiver / broad beam (Experiment 1)

2.1 Experiment Setup

During the first experiment, the whole ATOMIC unit including GNSS receiver and antenna as well as MCU were exposed to a broad beam (c.f. *Figure 1*). To test the functionality of the GNSS receiver and antenna, a GNSS re-radiation kit was used to transmit GNSS signals from a Signal Simulator to the radiation chamber. The experiment was carried out over approximately four hours with different beam settings.

Table 1 - Experiment 1 setup

Hardware	
Component	whole board
ATOMIC Board	In beam
GNSS receiver	In beam
GNSS Reradiation Kit	In use
Experiment Time	
Start Date Real	2024-10-05, 15:54:00
End Date Real	2024-10-05, 20:03:25
Beam properties	
Width	Broad
x [mm]	10.0
y [mm]	-20.0

Figure 1 - Experiment 1: Testing the MCU as well as GNSS receiver and antenna using a GNSS re-radiation kit

Table 2 - Experiment 1 timeline

Test	Beam			Energy [MeV]	Fluence		Flux		Dose	
	Start	End	Time [s]		Target [p/cm ²]	Actual [p/cm ²]	Current [nA]	Actual [p/cm ² /s]	Dose [rad]	Total dose [rad]
1	15:54:00	16:04:00	600	200.0	1.00E+11	9.02E+09	1.00E+00	5.01E+06	525	525
1	16:04:00	16:14:00	600	200.0	1.00E+11	9.02E+09	5.00E-01	5.01E+06	525	525
1	16:14:00	16:24:01	601	200.0	1.00E+11	9.02E+09	2.50E-01	5.01E+06	525	525
2	16:38:00	16:46:00	480	200.0	1.00E+11	1.39E+09	3.50E-01	2.80E+06	81	605
3	16:52:00	17:23:03	1863	200.0	1.00E+11	8.32E+09	5.00E-01	4.47E+06	484	1090
4	17:29:59	18:00:33	1834	151.18	1.00E+11	7.26E+09	5.00E-01	3.96E+06	508	1600
5	18:03:00	18:24:10	1270	101.34	1.00E+11	4.03E+09	5.00E-01	3.17E+06	373	1970
6	18:32:01	18:42:00	599	50.8	1.00E+11	1.11E+10	5.00E-01	7.01E+06	1730	3700
6	18:42:00	18:58:21	981	50.8	1.00E+11	1.11E+10	1.00E+00	7.01E+06	1730	3700
7	19:03:00	19:23:36	1236	29.31	1.00E+11	4.67E+09	1.00E+00	3.78E+06	1120	4820
8	19:29:00	19:39:00	600	16.04	1.00E+11	1.37E+10	1.00E+00	7.90E+06	5250	10100
8	19:39:00	19:44:00	300	16.04	1.00E+11	1.37E+10	5.00E+00	7.90E+06	5250	10100
8	19:44:00	19:48:30	270	16.04	1.00E+11	1.37E+10	1.00E+01	7.90E+06	5250	10100
8	19:48:30	19:49:00	30	16.04	1.00E+11	1.37E+10	1.00E+01	7.90E+06	5250	10100
8	19:49:00	19:50:30	90	16.04	1.00E+11	1.37E+10	1.00E+01	7.90E+06	5250	10100
8	19:50:30	19:52:30	120	0.0	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0	0
8	19:52:30	19:53:30	60	16.04	1.00E+11	1.37E+10	1.00E+01	7.90E+06	5250	10100
8	19:53:30	19:55:00	90	0.0	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0	0
8	19:55:00	19:56:00	60	16.04	1.00E+11	1.37E+10	1.00E+01	7.90E+06	5250	10100
8	19:56:00	19:57:30	90	0.0	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0	0
8	19:57:30	20:03:25	355	16.04	1.00E+11	1.37E+10	1.00E+00	7.90E+06	5250	10100

2.2 Results and Discussion

Figure 2 shows the telemetry output of the MCU during the results, while Figure 4 shows the beam settings. Beam energy and flux current were incrementally decreased in the beginning, to find settings where the hardware component resets occur less frequent. Afterwards, at lower energy levels (≤ 50 MeV), flux and flux current values were increased to test the reaction of the individual hardware components. It can clearly be seen that the MCU resets vanish after the energy is at or below 50 MeV, except for the final 30 min, where both flux and flux current were set to very high values. The GNSS receiver, however, resets frequently during all beam settings, indicating a generally high sensitivity to radiation. Figure 3 shows the telemetry of the GNSS receiver, where it can be seen that the receiver cannot continuously calculate a PVT. However, these results also indicate that the GNSS antenna is working properly and its internal low-noise amplifier is not visibly affected by the radiation.

The results for the temperature measurements of MCU and GNSS receiver shown in [Table 3 - Current and temperature statistics during experiment 1](#) indicate no significant temperature changes outside the expected range during nominal operations, and area also well within the hardware specifications. The current measurements indicate that during some latch-ups, e.g. at 18:55 or 19:40, the respective components seem to stay in an undefined state where they consume an almost constant current until they are reset. This indicates that some of the latch-ups might not be detected by the latch-up protections. While some adjustments to the latch-up resistor layout can be made, the MCU watchdog might also still be able to reset the system in such scenarios.

Table 3 - Current and temperature statistics during experiment 1

	Mean	Std	Median	Min	Max
Temperature MCU [°C]	43.1	0.7	43.0	40.0	47.0
Temperature GNSS RX [°C]	54.0	1.9	53.0	49.0	59.0
Current Multimeter [mA]	177.3	45.3	197.3	0	242.5

Figure 2 - Broad beam results for current consumption, temperature and uptimes of MCU and GNSS receiver

Figure 3 - GNSS receiver telemetry with position, velocity and time (PVT) as well as frontend parameters

Figure 4 - Beam settings for the broad beam experiment

3. ATOMIC Board with GNSS receiver / narrow beam (Experiment 2)

3.1 Experiment Setup

The second experiment has a similar setup to the first one as depicted in *Figure 1*. However, a narrow beam was used and pointed on the MCU, leaving the GNSS receiver out of direct radiation. Again, a GNSS re-radiation kit was used to transmit GNSS signals from a Signal Simulator to the radiation chamber. The experiment was carried out over approximately 2:15 hours with different beam settings.

Table 4 - Experiment 2 setup

Hardware	
Component	whole board
ATOMIC Board	In beam
GNSS receiver	Not in beam
GNSS Reradiation Kit	In use
Experiment Time	
Start Date Real	2024-10-05, 20:58:00
End Date Real	2024-10-05, 22:15:59
Beam properties	
Width	Narrow
x [mm]	-1.5
y [mm]	18.0

Table 5 - Experiment 2 timeline

Test	Beam			Energy [MeV]	Fluence		Flux		Dose	
	Start	End	Time [s]		Target [p/cm ²]	Actual [p/cm ²]	Current [nA]	Actual [p/cm ² /s]	Dose [rad]	Total dose [rad]
1	20:58:00	21:14:00	960	200.0	1.00E+11	1.00E+11	1.00E+00	4.04E+07	5820	15900
1	21:14:00	21:39:20	1520	200.0	1.00E+11	1.00E+11	5.00E+00	4.04E+07	5820	15900
2	21:42:59	21:57:40	881	101.34	1.00E+11	5.32E+10	5.00E+00	2.96E+07	4930	20800
2	21:57:40	22:13:00	920	101.34	1.00E+11	5.32E+10	1.00E+01	2.96E+07	4930	20800
3	22:15:59	22:36:39	1240	50.8	1.00E+11	2.13E+10	1.00E+01	1.72E+07	3330	24100

3.2 Results and Discussion

As for the first experiment, it can be seen in *Figure 5*, that the resets due to SEEs occur at the highest rates during beam times with maximum energy (200 MeV). Especially in the second phase of the experiment, where the flux current is increased from 1 nA to 5nA while keeping 200 MeV, the MCU resets on average more than once per minute. Higher flux current values of 10 nA in combination with lower energy levels of 100 MeV also cause the MCU to reset frequently. However, at energy levels of 50 MeV, even a flux current of 10 nA only causes a single reset over 20 minutes.

As seen in the temperature plot, two events at approximately 21:20 and 22:00 cause drastic temperature rises in the MCU. This indicates significantly higher than nominal current consumptions. However, as these events only last for very short durations, it can be concluded that the latch-up protections successfully sense the increased current consumption and cut the MCU power off to avoid damage due to over-heating.

While the GNSS receiver is not in the beam's main lobe and thus only receives stray radiation, its reset counts and frequency are similar or even slightly higher than for the MCU. *Figure 6* indicates that the receiver cannot acquire a PVT most of the time. This is due to the frequent resets, which cause a reboot of the GNSS receiver. The reboot in combination with the reacquisition of the signals takes approximately 1-2 min, which is often too long before the next reset occurs. This shows a significantly higher sensitivity to radiation for the GNSS receiver compared to the MCU, which has already been observed in the previous experiment.

Table 6 - Current and temperature statistics for experiment 2

	Mean	Std	Median	Min	Max
Temperature MCU [°C]	44.2	2.2	44.0	38.0	63.0
Temperature GNSS RX [°C]	5.4	2.5	54.0	45.0	58.0
Current Multimeter [mA]	169.2	55.3	198.1	0.0	316.9

Figure 5 - Narrow beam results for current consumption, temperature and uptimes of MCU and GNSS receiver

Figure 6 - GNSS receiver telemetry with position, velocity and time (PVT) as well as frontend parameters

Figure 7 - Beam settings for the narrow beam experiment with GNSS receiver and MCU

4. ATOMIC Board main power supply / narrow beam (Experiment 3)

4.1 Experiment Setup

In a third experiment, the main power supply of the ATOMIC board was exposed to a narrow radiation beam. The power supply consists of multiple electronic components. Its purpose is to accept an unregulated DC power supply between 9-22 V as input, regulate and downconvert it to provide regulated voltage levels of 5 V and 3.3 V for the different ATOMIC hardware components such as MCU or GNSS receiver. The test was carried out over 15 min.

Figure 8 - Experiment setup for the power supply radiation exposure

Table 7 - Experiment 3 timeline

Test	Beam			Energy [MeV]	Fluence		Flux		Dose	
	Start	End	Time [s]		Target [p/cm ²]	Actual [p/cm ²]	Current [nA]	Actual [p/cm ² /s]	Dose [rad]	Total dose [rad]
1	23:16:00	23:30:17	857	200.0	1e11	1e11	1e1	1.17e8	5820	30000

4.2 Results and Discussion

As seen in Figure 9, the 15 minute direct exposure to radiation had no visible effect on the main power supply, with the current and temperature levels being nominal over the whole experiment duration. Thus, the power supply is deemed to be sufficiently tolerant to radiation for the use case of the ATOMIC payload.

Figure 9 - Narrow beam results for power supply radiation exposure including current consumption, temperature and uptimes of MCU

Figure 10 - Beam settings for the power supply narrow beam experiment

5. ATOMIC Board MCU latchup protection / narrow beam (Experiment 4)

5.1 Experiment Setup

In a final experiment, the latch-up protection circuit on the ATOMIC board was exposed to direct radiation with a narrow beam. The general experiment setup is identical to the previous experiment 3 (c.f. *Figure 8*). The test was again carried out over 15 min using the same beam settings.

Table 8 - Experiment 4 timeline

Test	Beam			Energy [MeV]	Fluence		Flux		Dose	
	Start	End	Time [s]		Target [p/cm ²]	Actual [p/cm ²]	Current [nA]	Actual [p/cm ² /s]	Dose [rad]	Total dose [rad]
1	23:39:00	23:53:16	856	200.0	1e1	1e11	1e1	1.17e8	5820	35800

5.2 Results and Discussion

As for the previous experiment, the latch-up protection circuit showed no sensitivity to the exposed radiation, rendering it sufficiently radiation tolerant for the ATOMIC payload.

Figure 11 - Narrow beam results for latch-up protection radiation exposure including current consumption, temperature and uptimes of MCU

Figure 12 - Beam settings for the latch-up protection narrow beam experiment

6. Conclusion

The goal of the experiment was to assess the ATOMIC board with its individual hardware components. In experiment 1 and 2, both MCU and GNSS receiver were assessed. The results clearly demonstrated that the MCU can sustain without resets under certain radiation conditions, namely at lower energies (<50 MeV) and lower flux currents of around 1 nA. The GNSS receiver, however, exhibited a significant sensitivity to radiation, even if it was not put in the main lobe of the beam (experiment 2). This resulted in frequent resets, which often did not allow the receiver to stay of for more than 2 min, the time it requires to boot and acquire GNSS signals to output a PVT. The power supply and latch-up protections, which were tested in experiments 3 and 4, respectively, did not show any malfunctioning when directly exposed to radiation.

Sometimes during the first two experiments, one or more components entered an undefined state after a latch-up, causing them to consume an apparently random but constant amount of current. This indicates that the latch-up protection is not capable of detecting all latch-ups yet, and might be subject to tuning. Furthermore, an independent hardware watchdog could help in such situations by resetting the whole system.

During the overall duration of the four experiments, a total dose of approximately 35 krad was accumulated. Notably, none of the components, including even the GNSS receiver, received permanent damage throughout the tests, and the overall ATOMIC unit was still functioning nominally afterwards. It remains to be tested if the tested unit experienced some kind of degradation during the experiments, which could e.g. be observed in a slightly higher current consumption or higher operating temperatures.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	
Follow-up experiment at same facility	X
Follow-up experiment at another facility	X
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

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